

THE INFLUENCE OF INDIVIDUAL FACTORS ON THE ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION

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ABSTRACT

Today, no one is safe from forces and pressures, which are exerted on it, because of a significant number of the requirements in particular as regards competitiveness, the need for change, or the crises and the deregulations. In front of the economic and social turbulences which we know, the creation of new company appears as a cause of general interest. This research papers focuses on the problematic of the entrepreneurship, and more particularly on the stake which this domain represents in our society, by treating the determinants of the entrepreneurial intention. To face this news gives, students must reconsider their behaviors and their practices to renew themselves, to open out and reinforce their position in the market. Some of these practices form what one calls the entrepreneurial orientation. For this reason, we will devote this paper for better encircling and apprehending the concept of individual factors, and we tried to know how the individual factors (motivations, need for accomplishment, need for autonomy, passion to develop its own idea, individual characteristics, work experience, teaching) can influence the intention of the entrepreneur to create his own project. We focused on review literature through a survey of a sample of students from the Higher Institute of Business Administration of Sfax (Tunisia).

KEYWORDS

individual factors, motivational, need for achievement, need for autonomy, passion to develop its own idea, individual characteristics, work experience, teaching, intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

The entrepreneurship occupies a more and more important place in the state economies. From then on, many authors consider that the new business start-up is a major stake for the development of any nation as far as it is the main source of wealth and fight against the unemployment (Moreau, 2004). For that reason, Baccari (2006), maintain that the similarities and the gaps between countries are a function, essentially, of differences at the level of the rates of employment and creation of new companies. With the fast evolution of the more and more complex technologies and the globalization of the economy, a particular interest was granted to the creation and to the development of the innovative companies in hardly contained by knowledge.

In Tunisia, the entrepreneurship takes advantage of a big attention on behalf of several actors. Such an attention attributed to the entrepreneurship is explained by the recognition of the essential role of the entrepreneurship in the economic development of countries. So, the diverse actions which were taken in favor of the entrepreneurship in Tunisia demonstrate the will of this country to encourage the private initiative.

The domain of the entrepreneurship does not stop knowing a quick and unprecedented development. This joins under the assistance of the visionary will of the Tunisian public authorities to reduce the problem of unemployment, on one hand, and to display an entrepreneurial culture being embodied in the development of the entrepreneurial action, on the other hand.

Finally, in front of the economic and social turbulences which we know, the creation of new company appears as a cause of general interest. This research papers focuses on the problematic of the entrepreneurship, and more particularly on the stake which this domain represents in our society, by treating the determinants of the entrepreneurial intention. The purpose of that research consists in explaining the influence of the individual factors on the entrepreneurial intention and to test it in the Tunisian context.

Then, we were devising our work in five sections. In the first one, we present a review of the literature and the development of the hypotheses, the second will limit itself to the methodological choices, the third concentrates on the purification of the scales of the measures, in the fourth we shall clarify the test of the hypotheses with the interpretation, and finally we present the discussion of the results.

To advance the impact of the individual factors on the intention, we define, at first, the entrepreneurial intention. Secondly, we shall present the individual factors and specifying the hypotheses by resulting for this study.

2. THE ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION

For Fayolle and Gaily (2009), the intention is the cognitive demonstration of the will of a person to exercise a behavior. It is considered as a good proxy of strategic and controllable human behavior. For him, the intention, in a theory very used in the sciences of the behavior, is the result of three abstract antecedents which we are going to present by applying them to the case of the creation of the new company. Attitudes to the behavior constitute the first antecedent. The intention to create a company is a function of the degree of favorable or unfavorable evaluation of the behavior in question. Therefore, if we want to have an intention to create company, it is necessary that favorable attitudes towards the behavior are skilled. Different places like for example the family, the territories, and the occupations can act on these attitudes. Schools, universities, awareness-raising activities also occupy an important role (Shapero and Sokol, 1982).

The second antecedent presents the received social standards. The intention to create a company depends on perceptions that the individual has notices of the persons or the social groups (my friends, my family, and my professors) which matter for him with regard to the envisaged behavior. These social standards perceived by the individual are more particularly resultant of the places evoked above and is influenced by cultural and societal variables (Shapero and Sokol, 1982). The received controllability, finally, is the third and last antecedent. The intention is function of opportunities and difficulties perceived in the hypothesis where the behavior would arise.

3. INDIVIDUAL FACTORS

We cannot talk about entrepreneur by skipping over the deep strengths, which animate him: the motivations, the individual characteristics and the qualities, which are connected to the personality of the individual, occupied a considerable role.

3.1. Motivational

The motivational can be the result of the personal success, social success as benefactor or for the reputation, which the creation allows to acquire. Shapero (1982) confirmed that the motivation is the result of a need for independence, of the desire to be his own boss and the look for the autonomy. He can involve also need for achievement and for change.

3.2. Need for achievement

In a contemporary society where we are forced to give always the best of our self to circumscribe, the future entrepreneur is looking for of the social recognition and the personal realization. One of the main characteristics of the entrepreneurial behavior is the need of achievement that is the need to excel and to reach certain purpose in an objective of personal achievement. This need for achievement is generally more important than the person's who prefer spots containing a challenge in spots creatures of routine. Somewhere, the entrepreneurship is the outcome of a professional career, we begin by being salaried and then we become an entrepreneur (Gergen and al, 1992).

The works of Clelland (1961, 1965, and 1969) popularized this notion of need for accomplishment as being an essential characteristic of an entrepreneur and contributed to his development. Today, we cannot neglect the importance of this attribute, but we can also consider it as being an indicator. In other words the need for achievement can serve to distinguish, in a population, the creators from the not creators (Janssen, 2006).

3.3. Need for autonomy

According to Davidsson (1995), the need for autonomy is present with person who prefers to set up their own objectives in the first time, to develop the action plans and to check themselves the realization of their objectives in the second time. These persons try to avoid the limitations, the roles established in organizations, and then they choose an independent activity. The persons who have a high degree of autonomy would of course feel at ease in an entrepreneurial activity. This desire was generally found with the entrepreneur's who spent several years in the service of a society. He feels then the need to create his own organization, to make his own experiences. Working according to rules which he fixed himself, he installs his own workspace, he establishes a work atmosphere which suits him most, and which corresponds most to its culture. For the reason of having many years of experience, he feels a desire of independence and auto control (Janssen, 2006).

3.4. Passion to develop its own idea

The idea is private and it is appropriated to the person when he believes in it. A sense of subjective attachment was shown, and the person who had the idea of creation, consider himself the most concerned person (Jeff Brice, 2002).

The idea can be the result of discovering a new product, a new technique and a new know-how, especially for engineers and technicians who invent new processes. To build an idea, it is interesting to take place in the good networks and to see frequently the good actors. For example a person who is interested by the new business start-up can participate in creations, help creators, and turn as employee at first towards professional sectors and search for jobs connected with the new business start-up. It is necessary to develop an attitude to make the sponge, thus it is necessary to know how to take advantage of meetings and of fortuitous discoveries in all the places of the personal and the professional lives. The quotidian life, the family, the hobbies, the

leisure activities, can offer occasions so in the company where we work; the contacts and the exchanges with the stakeholders, the suppliers and the customers are also fertile places. When we want to become an entrepreneur, the most difficult things are not to have an idea but rather to know how the ideas are and how they can be captured (Boissin, 2009). H1: the motivation influences positively the entrepreneurial intention.

3.5. Individual characteristics

As for the qualities and the individual characteristics, we retain the age, the sex, the self-confidence, the resourcefulness, the capacity to take risks, the creativity, the adaptability, the ease to hear each other, to spread his energy, to be believed in the control of its fate and an obvious capacity to be worked (Ajzen.I., 1991). This research shows us how much the entrepreneur is the resultant of a combination of characteristics, sometimes innate or acquired. A person could possess an entrepreneurial potential but not the capacity to create a company. Does the question of age and sex really exist? If we compare the age of the creators, the average varies enormously according to countries, and the area is very important. Furthermore, we concentrate our study on the students and the young graduates. We thus emit the postulate that the studied population is young.

H 2: the individual characteristics act positively on the entrepreneurial intention.

3.6. Work experience

The acquired work experience is considered as the most important individual factor; it is to be considered in the opportunity to create companies. The knowledge specifies of a range of products, used technologies, markets, a particular know-how establish experiences and assets which turn out useful during the creation of a company in which the activity is close or similar of the previously led activity.

In any event, the knowledge of the life in company provokes the relations between actors, the quality-notion of services would be and the work experience seems to count. According to Fayolle (2009), the entrepreneurs create their companies after having worked in sectors close to the business sector of the new company where they acquired their skills and their experiences with the product and the used technology and then they possess a good knowledge about markets, technologies and industry.

H3: the work experience acts positively on the entrepreneurial intention.

3.7. Teaching

In the domain of the professional teaching, the teachers can form rapports with the staff of companies, occurring in the educational plan or welcoming students in teaching course. The occasions of interactions bound connected to the formation are numerous, for example the participation in juries, reception, order of collective works with educational character and professional, teaching course, visit of companies, partnership of implementation of formations and depend partly on the educational inventiveness of the teachers. A plan of formation is thus an organization, which, by its functioning, arouses occasions of meeting, interactions between students, permanent teachers, and finally professionals more or less regular "participants who are the "intervening teacher ".

These three types of actors constitute an organized system of action pressed on the plan of formation: the students developed expanding links of hiring and once become hired the new

contacts of the plan of teaching; the employers look for candidates; the person in charge of the plan of teaching maintains the functioning of the system and places his students. All these interactions ends in the creation of a particular density of links between the plan of teaching and the particular professional space at which it aims, in a point of concentration of the relations with the professional places. For Coleman (1990), it produces then a collective share capital appropriate to the educational organization, efficient from the point of view of the conditions of access to the employment for the students. Just like the education, the professional teaching plays an important role, which can arouse vocations and make sensitive a large public in the entrepreneurship.

For Fayolle (2009), the skills required for an entrepreneur can be the object of learning. It will be about the acquisition of knowledge in business, about the understanding of a profile of a company, about the analysis of the growth, about the sense of the ethics, about the capacity of seeing and about seizing business opportunities.

The companies of growth are based on founders endowed with a high educational level at the same time stemming from the world of the technologies and from the business world. In this perspective, universities and big schools of engineers and management generally restructured their teachings in the prism of the entrepreneurship: options, specialized networks, dedicated master's degrees multiplied, competitions subsidize projects or students companies; the entrepreneurs invest classrooms and come to testify of their experiences enthusiastically. He also learns to give realism to an exploratory idea: tools and methods of analysis of market and model business, or still constitution of team and calculation of the financial forecasts, without forgetting the "mythical" business plan, instill the dose of reason necessary for the credibilisation of the act to undertake. In this context, the contacts are formed between students, professors, entrepreneurs witnesses, professionals of the finance, the council representatives of establish keys and give some more of closeness and tangibility of more adventure in entrepreneurship (Fayolle, 2005).

H4: teaching influences positively the entrepreneurial intention.

Finally, we can formulate the following hypothesis:

H A: the individual factors act positively on the entrepreneurial intention.

The motivational for choice of career are at first all individual; we can say that they depend directly on the individual (his personality, her inner convictions, his values). The first researches in entrepreneurship validate this point of view. The models of "the character traits", also named "trait models", advance the psychological attributes of the entrepreneurs, often different from those of the non-entrepreneurs.

4. THE METHODOLOGICAL CHOICES

To verify the proposals formulated previously, we expose successively the construction of the questionnaire, and the choice of the sample.

4.1. The construction of the questionnaire

In order to be closer from the theoretical study to the reality of the ground, we chose to make an investigation by using a quantitative method. The investigation was made through a questionnaire. We built this questionnaire by inspiring from previous works. The questionnaire was designed so as to reflect the factors which influence the intention to create a company. Our objective was simply to determine the point of view of the students that we investigated, we have

to discover if they consider these variables as brakes or if they consider them as engines in their intention to create a company.

4.2. Choice of the sample

Once the questionnaire was drafted and meadow tested, the following step consists in determining to whom and to how many persons this questionnaire was administered. The sample represents the group of people asked and supposed to represent the universe that cover the investigation sends.

The method of sampling is the one by suitability. D'Astous (2000, p. 193) say that a sample of suitability "consists of selected elements because they are available, easy to close or to convince to participate in the research". Indeed, for reasons of interests, the sample is formed by 250 students in the higher Institute of Business administration of Sfax.

5. PURIFICATION OF THE SCALES OF MEASURE

The validity and the reliability are both the most criteria retained to estimate the researches in sciences of management. We shall define each of these qualities and we shall expose the measures which we preserved to verify them in our research. The purification is made first of all through the test of Kaiser-Meyer-Okin (KMO). His measure must be acceptable and must have a value superior than 0, 5 translating consequently the inter correlation of variables. In the second time, we make the test of sphericity of Bartlett which supplies the statistical probability (0, 5 % threshold) that the correlation between the items of the scale is different than zero.

This test must be significant in order to have a factorisable data. That's why a factorial analysis in main component with orthogonal rotation (varimax) was led. This will allow us to consider the dimensionality of every variable. We use the psychometric approach which consists in eliminating from the factorial analysis, the items considered unacceptable, and in proceeding an iterative way until the obtaining of a stable factorial structure. Furthermore, we must verify the coefficient Alpha which measures the internal coherence between the various items of the measure.

The variance is calculated from the initial appropriate value which, itself, is dependent on the number of variables at first. By hypothesis we look for dimensions and so that they explain more than $1/NB$ of the dimensions %, that is to say that it is more than a variable. In this case we hold the dimensions which explain more than $1/29=3,448\%$. An appropriate value of 1 corresponds to 3,448 %. An appropriate value of 7,644 allow to explain $7,644 \times 3,448\% = 26,358\%$.

The accumulated variance 89, 275 % allows to estimate if the reduction of 29 variables in 9 components allows keeping the main part of the phenomenon measured by 29 of the first time. Index of KMO is also 0,644, which means that all the items are averagely coherent. Our test of Bartlett is significant, thus our factorial model is suited.

The homogeneity of this scale can be considered as satisfactory, because our alpha is equal to 0, 8802. Our scale is reliable and usable for the later analyses.

6. TEST OF THE HYPOTHESES AND THE INTERPRETATION

Model1: impact of the motivation on the entrepreneurial intention.

To estimate the quality of the adjustment of this regression, we have to employ the test F of FISHER-SNEDECOR. We must clarify that, in the studied sample, for the risk α considered, multiple R2 is significantly different from 0 (Giannelonni and Vernet, 1995). The critical value of F, in the threshold $\alpha = 0,05$, for 1 and 97 degrees of freedom, is equal to 4. The calculated F (5,973, sig. = 0,016) being clearly upper, we can conclude that the quality of the adjustment offered by the regression is significant. There is thus a significant dependence between the motivations and the entrepreneurial intention. The global model is significant at the threshold of 5 % (sig 0,0160, 05) with a value of Fisher of 5,973, we thus end that the meditative data allow us to affirm that there is a strongly significant influence of the motivations on the entrepreneurial intention.

For the model 2: check of the influence of the individual characteristics on the entrepreneurial intention.

Concerning the quality of the adjustment of this regression, we have to employ the test F of FISHER-SNEDECOR. We must clarify that, in the studied sample, for the risk α considered, multiple R2 is significantly different from 0 (Giannelonni and Vernet, 1995, p. 482). The critical value of F, in the threshold $\alpha = 0,05$, for 2 and 96 degrees of freedom, is equal to 3,15. The calculated F (5,063, sig. = 0,008) being clearly upper, we can conclude that the quality of the adjustment offered by the regression is significant. There is thus a significant dependence between the individual characteristics and the entrepreneurial intention. The overall model is significant at the 5% (sig = 0.008 < 0,05) with a value of 5,063 Fisher, we conclude that the data used to decide in favor of a highly significant influence of individual characteristics on entrepreneurial intention.

For Model 3: Impact of experience on entrepreneurial intention.

To estimate the quality of the adjustment of this regression, we have to employ the test F of FISHER-SNEDECOR. We must clarify that, in the studied sample, for the risk α considered, multiple R2 is significantly different from 0 (Giannelonni and Vernet, 1995). The critical value of F, in the threshold $\alpha = 0.05$, for 3 and 95 degrees of freedom is equal to 2.76. The calculated F (5.063, sig. = 0.002) was significantly higher, we can conclude that the quality of the adjustment of this regression is significant. There is therefore a significant dependence between the experience and entrepreneurial intention. The overall model is significant at the 5% (sig = 0.002 < 0,05) with a value of 5,137 Fisher, we conclude that the data used to decide in favor of a highly significant influence of experience professional on the entrepreneurial intention.

For Model 4: the influence of teaching on entrepreneurial intention

In order to estimate the quality of the adjustment of this regression, we have to employ the test F of FISHER-SNEDECOR. The critical value of F, in the threshold $\alpha = 0.05$, for 4 and 94 degrees of freedom is equal to 2.52. The calculated F (4.991, sig. = 0.001) was significantly higher, we can conclude that the quality of the adjustment of this regression is significant. There is therefore a significant dependence between teaching and entrepreneurial intention. The overall model is significant at the 5% (sig = 0.001 < 0,05) with a value of 4.991 Fisher, we conclude that the data used to decide in favor of a highly significant influence of the formation on the entrepreneurial intentions.

Table 1. ANNOVA

Model		Sum of squares	Ddl	Mean square	F	Significance
1	Regression	5,647	1	5,647	5,973	,016
	Residue	91,706	97	,945		
	Total	97,354	98			
2	Regression	9,288	2	4,644	5,063	,008
	Residue	88,065	96	,917		
	Total	97,354	98			
3	Regression	13,589	3	4,530	5,137	,002
	Residue	83,764	95	,882		
	Total	97,354	98			
4	Regression	17,054	4	4,264	4,991	,001
	Residue	80,299	94	,854		
	Total	97,354	98			

To identify significant links between motivations, individual characteristics, work experience, teaching and entrepreneurial intention, we have to apply the multiple regression analysis. Indeed, this technique is suitable for cases where the explicative and to be explained variables are quantitative.

The R² named linear coefficient of determination is the main indicator of the quality of a regression. It is considered as the part of the variance of the dependent variable explained by the independent variable. It units the ability of the regression to represent the shade of observed values. Moreover this coefficient is close to 1, the restitution of these values is so good. However, the significance of the result must be interpreted according to the number of observations and variables that are included in the calculation of adjusted (Evrard et al, 2003). "The Adjusted R² is the best realistic measure, and then it may be habitually lower than the R² "normal".

The theoretical value of the Durbin-Watson statistic is close to 2 (1.998), which confirms the lack of correlation between the residuals.

For Model 1: The estimation of this model shows a linear adjustment in the range of 0.058 of R² and 0.048 of R² adjusted. Regression testing, whose characteristics are collected in the table of multiple regression indicates the reference population for a good correlation between motivation and entrepreneurial intention. The intensity of this relationship is expressed by a coefficient (correlation R) whose value is 24.1 %. This result indicates that the model returns 5.8 % of the variation expressed from the beginning.

Model 2: Before proceeding with the analysis of the results produced by the regression, we must first check the validity of the model. The estimate shows a linear adjustment in the order of 0.095 in terms of R² and 0.077 for the R² adjusted. The regression test shows a good correlation between motivation and entrepreneurial intention. The intensity of this relationship is expressed by a coefficient whose value is 30.9 %. This result indicates that the model returns 9.5 % of the variation expressed from the beginning.

Estimation of the model 3 shows a linear adjustment in the order of 0.140 in terms of R² and 0.112 for the R² adjusted. The regression test indicates for the reference population a good correlation between motivation and entrepreneurial intention. The intensity of this relationship

results in a correlation coefficient R whose value is 37.4%. This result indicates that the model reproduces 14% of the variation expressed from the beginning.

For Model 4: There is a linear adjustment in the range of 0.175 of R² and 0.140 for the R² adjusted. The regression test indicates the existence of a good correlation between motivation and entrepreneurial intention. The intensity of this relationship is expressed by a coefficient equal to 41.9%. This result indicates that the model returns 17.5% of the variation expressed from the beginning.

Table 2. Multiple Regressions

	R	R-deux	R-deux ajusté	Error standard of estimation	Durbin-Watson
Model					
1	,241	,058	,048	,97233	
2	,309	,095	,077	,95778	
3	,374	,140	,112	,93901	
4	,419	,175	,140	,92426	1,998

For Model 1: motivations act positively on the entrepreneurial intention, with a significant regression coefficient beta = 0.241, and with positive sign.

For model 2: we find that no significant correlation between individual characteristics and the entrepreneurial intention, this is reflected in the negative sign of the regression coefficient beta = -0.196.

About Model 3: the experience has a positive contribution in relation to the entrepreneurial intention with a regression coefficient beta = 0.212 significant and with positive sign.

Finally, for Model 4: The regression coefficient beta = 0.241 is significant and with positive sign. So the independent variable, which is “teaching”, positively affects the entrepreneurial intention.

Based on this analysis we can conclude that just only one hypothesis was not confirmed:

H 1: motivational factors positively influence the entrepreneurial intention. Confirmed.

H 2: Individual characteristics have a positive effect on entrepreneurial intention. Not confirmed.

H 3: Professional experience has a positive effect on entrepreneurial intention. Confirmed.

H 4: The teaching positively influences entrepreneurial intention. Confirmed.

H A: Individual factors have a positive effect on entrepreneurial intention. Confirmed.

7. DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

Using the analyses performed throughout this empirical investigation, in the Tunisian context, we were able to meet our object of research, which is to determine the effect of different factors on the individual entrepreneurial intention.

Our sample consisted of 250 students in the terminal phase of their academic curriculum and soon searching for job, their behavior is a function of the determinants of entrepreneurial intention.

Moreover, by the use of regression analysis of the data we found that motivation, work experience and teaching have a significant impact on the intention. Furthermore, we did not find statistically significant relationships between individual characteristics (age and sex) and

entrepreneurial intention, but it was shown at the global level, that individual factors have a positive effect on the intention entrepreneurial.

Indeed, if we compare empirically, the results obtained in the framework of our research, with those found in other studies, we can conclude that our intentional model has an important explanatory power, since we have empirically validated the majority of our assumptions.

8. CONCLUSION

To test the validity of the research model, we used multiple regression techniques, correlation and ANOVA for one factor; they have to update explanatory and predictive factors of entrepreneurial intention. When we allow the data and the questionnaire, we performed quantitative analyzes to better identify and describe the factors that significantly influence entrepreneurial intention.

Individual factors (motivation, experience and teaching), among other contextual factors are explanatory and predictive variables of entrepreneurial intention. Combined in a model, these factors proved relevant in the context of the reference sample.

However, H 2 was not validated in the model. Our research certainly has a "positive" approach to validating assumptions. But the audit did not mean demonstration. Establish a hypothesis is invalid in itself an interesting result that can illuminate further research dealing with the intention as an important phase of the entrepreneurial process.

Thus, with respect to H2, we reported that individual characteristics do not affect the entrepreneurial intention.

The validation of a model of entrepreneurial intention brings new knowledge to the field of entrepreneurship. The research process that we conducted provides further theoretical and practical benefits, but also has limitations while paving the way for extensions it seems necessary to explore.

Our findings show the importance of these factors in the entrepreneurial intention. The importance of the impact of factors on intention reveals the intention increases, significantly, with the influence by the latter. Indeed, this result shows the importance of entrepreneurial education in universities. Today, with the rise in unemployment among graduates, academic institutions are challenged to train and sensitize graduates, through various educational processes, creating their own businesses.

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